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TECHNOLOGY
CHEMICAL PROFILING AND ADME PREDICTION OF SARACA ASOCA (ROXB)
WILDE

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ABSTRACT

The type of qualitative research through the phenomenological approach, the results showed that the concept of community empowerment plays an important role in building community self-reliance, so far the concept of poverty handling is more To the short-term program, where the effect is only short-term has no impact on the change of mindset and economic independence, therefore, the policy of poverty management needs to be accompanied by the program of Thinking self-reliance program Packaged in such a way.

KEYWORDS: Poverty, policy, strategy, service, independence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Poverty is one of the problems that arise in building together with the unemployment problem and the gap that the three hooks are hook. In the context of development in Indonesia, the problem of poverty has been increasingly a year since the economic crisis struck Indonesia in the middle of 1997 ago. Poverty is becoming increasingly common because of the increasing number of poor people who are sharply caused by the economic crisis. The poverty in Indonesia now has become a national society that is the Government of Indonesia is working to eradicate the Indonesian population from the problem of poverty. Poverty is a problem that has an attachment to social problems in Indonesia. For example, the poor family has a relatively minimal level of livelihood and health than the person whose life has been fulfilled.

Since the year 2002, a team consisting of Indonesian and foreign analysts, under the auspices of the poverty Analysis Program in Indonesia (INDOPOV) at the Jakarta World Bank Office, has studied the characteristics of poverty in Indonesia. They have sought to identify what is useful and beneficial in poverty alleviation efforts, and to clarify what choices are available to Governments and non-governmental organizations in an effort to To improve the standards and quality of life of the poor.

One of the main indicators of a country's economic growth can be seen from its poverty. Thus, poverty became one of the main themes in development. The success and failure of the development was measured based on changes in poverty (Suryahadi and Sumarto, 2001). Because poverty is a development problem characterized by unemployment, retardation, and backbreaking. Poor people are very weak in the ability to strive and have limited access to socio-economic activities. In such contexts, poverty is thus closely related to the capacity and number of people in the region itself.

A. Formula problems

1. How poverty is in Indonesia ?
2. How to strategy to alleviate poverty ?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The understanding of poverty

According to dictionary Bahasa Indonesia poverty is a condition in which there is a shortage of things that are common to be like food, clothing, shelter and drinking water, these things are closely related to the quality of life. Poverty sometimes also means the absence of access to education and jobs that are able to overcome the problem of poverty and gain worthy honors as citizens. Poverty is a global problem. Some people understand this term subjectively and comparatively, while others see it in a moral and evaluative sense, and others understand it from an established scientific angle. The term "Developing countries" is usually used to refer to countries that "poor".

➤ **Poverty is understood in many ways. The main understanding includes:**

- A description of the lack of material, which usually includes daily food needs, clothing, housing, and health services. Poverty in this sense is understood as a situation of scarcity of basic goods and services.
- An overview of social needs, including social alienation, dependence, and the inability to participate in society. This includes education and information. Social isolation is usually distinguished from poverty, as it covers political and moral issues, and is not restricted to the economic sphere.
- An overview of the lack of income and adequate wealth. The meaning of "adequate" here is very different across political and economic sections around the world.

While the head of the central Statistic Agency, Rusman Heriawan said a person is considered poor when he is unable to meet the minimum needs of life. Minimal life needs It is the need to consume food in a measure of 2100 pounds of calories per person per day and minimum needs of non food such as housing, education, health and transportation. "So there is a dietary requirement in calories and the need for non-food in rupiah. If the final collapse is Rp 182,636 per person per month," said Rusman Heriawan to the BBC. With that definition, the number of poor people in Indonesia in 2008 reached approximately 35 million inhabitants.

The figure is the result of a survey of national socio-economic, Susenas with samples only 68,000 households, whereas the number of households in Indonesia reaches 55 million. According to statisticians from Surabaya Institute of Technology, Kresnayana Yahya, the government's perspective on poverty does not reflect reality. "Some are not taken into account, the calorie destroyer. People smoke can be six to seven rods. That's actually negative. He can say the budget a few, but in it there are six-seven cigarettes," said Kresnayana Yahya.

B. Measuring poverty

Poverty can be grouped in two categories: absolute poverty and relative poverty. Absolute poverty refers to a consistent set of standards, unaffected by time and place/country. An example of an absolute measurement is the percentage of a population that eats under an adequate amount that sustains the needs of the human body (approximately 2000-2500 calories per day for adult males).

The World Bank defines absolute poverty as a living with revenues under USD \$1/day and middle poverty for revenues below \$2 per day, with this limit then estimated at 2001 1.1 billion people in the world consume less than \$1/day and 2.7 billion people in the world consume less than \$2/day. "The proportion of developing countries living in extreme poverty has dropped from 28% in 1990 to 21% in 2001. Looking at the period 1981-2001, the percentage of the world population living under the poverty line \$1 dollars/day has been reduced by half. However, the value of \$1 also decreased during this period.

Despite the most severe poverty in the developing world, there is evidence of the presence of poverty in each region. In developed countries, this condition presents homeless people who wander to and fro the poor suburbs and ghetto. Poverty can be seen as a collective condition of the poor, or a group of poor people, and in this sense the entire state is sometimes considered poor. To avoid this stigma, these countries are usually referred to as developing countries.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Types of qualitative research through the phenomenological approach

4. DISCUSSION

Poverty alleviation remains one of the most urgent problems in Indonesia. The number of Indonesians living with less than US \$2 per day is almost the same as the total population living with less than US \$2 per day from all countries in the East Asia region excluding China. The Government's commitment to eradicate poverty is stated in the Medium Term development plan (RPJM) 2005-2009, based on the national Strategy for Poverty Alleviation (SNPK). In addition to signing the Millennial development goals (or the Millennium Development Goals) for the year 2015, in its RPJM the government has compiled the principal objectives in poverty alleviation for the year 2009, including ambitious targets for Reducing poverty figures from 18.2 percent in 2002 to 8.2 percent in 2009. Although national poverty figures are approaching the before-crisis conditions, it still means that about 40 million people today live below the poverty line. Moreover, although Indonesia is now a middle-income country, the proportion of the living population with a income of less than US \$2 per day is the same as the low-income countries in the region, such as Vietnam.

There are three distinctive features of poverty in Indonesia. First, many households are around the national poverty line, which is equivalent to PPP US \$1,55-per day, so that many residents who are not relatively poor but vulnerable to poverty. Second, the measure of poverty is based on income, so it does not reflect the actual poverty limit. Many people who may not belong to (poor in terms of income) can be categorized as poor on the basis of lack of access to basic services as well as low human development indicators. Thirdly, given the vast and diverse region of Indonesia, the difference between regions is a fundamental characteristic of poverty in Indonesia.

1. Many Indonesians are vulnerable to poverty. The national poverty rate is a large number of people living just a little above the national poverty line. Nearly 42 percent of all people.

2. Poverty in terms of non income is a more serious problem than poverty in terms of income. The special areas that should be wary of are :

✓ High Nutritional (malnutrition) figures and even increases in recent years: one quarter of children under the age of five suffer from malnutrition in Indonesia, with poor nutritional numbers remaining in the last years despite the decline Poverty rate.

✓ Maternal health is much worse compared to the countries in the same region, the mortality rate in Indonesia is 307 (to 100,000 live births), three times greater than Vietnam and six times larger than China and Malaysia only About 72 percent of childbirth assisted by trained midwives.

✓ Weak educational outcomes. The numbers continued from elementary school to middle school were still low, especially among the poor people: among the age groups of 16-18 years in the poorest, only 55 percent graduated in junior high School, while the number for the richest kuintil is 89 percent for The same cohort.

✓ Low access to clean water, especially among the poor. For the lowest kuintil, only 48 percent have access to clean water in rural areas, while for urban, 78 percent.

✓ Access to sanitation is a crucial issue. Eighty percent of the poor in rural areas and 59 percent of the poor in urban areas do not have access to septic tanks, while they are only less than one percent of all Indonesians served by sewage sewer Piped

3. The difference between large regions in the field of poverty. Diversity between regions is characteristic of Indonesia, which is reflected by the differences between rural and urban areas. In rural areas, there are about 57 percent of poor people in Indonesia who also often do not have access to basic infrastructure services only about 50 percent of the poor in rural areas have access to clean water resources, Compared to 80 percent for poor urban communities. But importantly, by crossing the vast archipelago of Indonesia, there will be differences in the pockets of poverty within the region itself.

Many programs, but poverty remains high

When a direct cash subsidy (BLT) program ends, many suspect the poverty rate increases in 2007. The World Bank, for example, on the World Bank East Asia Update reported on November 2006, estimated the poverty rate next year will increase after the end of the SLT program. The conditional cash subsidy Program that will begin next year will be too small to dampen the impact of the SLT end.

The Indonesian team study rose more critically. The combination of economic observers in the team assessed the poverty rate must increase in this year considering the purchasing power of the people who continue to

decline. Then because of the end of the SLT, and unguided price of basic needs such as rising rice prices and cooking oil as well as flooding in some areas.

The poverty rate will only go down with two possibilities, making changes and engineering calculation methods. Secondly, making changes or cleaning samples of data is a very vulgar and manipulative way and very embarrassing both morally and intellectually. However, beyond the alleged poverty rate dropped 2.13 million people from last year. With the change of poverty line from Rp 151,997 per capita per month to Rp 166,697 per capita per month. The large number of poor people are heavily influenced by the poverty line because the poor population is the population that has average spending per capita per month below the poverty line.

The Central Statistic Agency (BPS) mentions that the increase in public income that is in the poverty line increases compared to the price increase of the underlying matter. In addition, although the price of rice rises, but balanced with the exellontorization of rice programs for the poor. BPS Judging even though the SLT expires but many poor people who can use money originating from the SLT to work informally. Related to this poverty, the world Bank's analysis shows, the difference between poor and almost poor people in Indonesia is very small.

The vulnerability for poor falls is very high in Indonesia. The world Bank mentions, there are three prominent traits of poverty in Indonesia. First, many households are around the poverty line which equates to US \$1.55 per day income. So that many people who are relatively poor, vulnerable to poverty.

Secondly, the size of poverty is based on income so it does not reflect the actual poverty limit. Many people may not belong to the poor in terms of income, but are categorized as poor on the basis of lack of access to basic services. And the low indicators of human development. Thirdly, given the vast and diverse region of Indonesia, the difference between regions is a fundamental characteristic of poverty in Indonesia.

While the funds are disbursed for the poverty program, judged not to touch directly to the problem of poverty. The poverty budget amounted to Rp 54 trillion in 2007 and Rp 62 trillion in 2008, according to Imam Sugema, from the value of Rp 54 trillion that directly in contact with poverty only Rp 5 trillion. Nevertheless, even though the poverty statistics in Indonesia are falling, but in fact, the economic gap between rich and poor in Indonesia is still sharp.

The amount of poor people, because the magnitude of the unemployment rate in Indonesia. Not absorbed by the workforce, because of the slow pace of expansion of the business sector. BPS Data showed, the number of working force in Indonesia in February 2007 reached 108.13 million people or increased 174 million people compared to the August 2006 workforce recorded at 106.39 million. From the addition of the workforce, the number of Indonesian people working in February this year reached 97.58 million. Thus, the number of unemployment in Indonesia still reaches 10.55 million people until February 2007.

However, if the Government is still not able to move the real sector, unemployment will still swell because the workforce continues to emerge and the number of population that can not be overcome as seen in the data period of March 2006 population Population of 221.328 million people to 224.177 million people in 2007.

The heavy duty for the current and government governments is further reducing poverty and unemployment. Sure we expect, the leaders of this country are no longer fragmented with the diverse desires of the party but rather become one to jointly overcome this problem of poverty and unemployment.

There is a kind of agreement, if poverty alleviation becomes the main motive of development policy, then procurement and increase income of poor people become the most important objective of all activities. However, in that connection, there are two different paradigms on how to reach them.

First, the belief that economic growth is the most efficacious medicine to alleviate poverty because it will absorb a lot of labor. However, empirical reality suggests the opposite. This is due to the rise of the production of solid capital and labor-saving.

Secondly, the belief that poor people should be assisted to earn income. The small and Medium enterprises (SMES) sector are believed to be the main joints of the people's economy. The assumption is that when the equation of opportunity with capital solid effort is available, then a small medium business is believed to be able to increase investment, business development, and income. Unfortunately, as a first paradigm, there has been no convincing empirical evidence to support the correctness of the assumption. Based on the two paradigms above, it is presumably that there is no instant prescription that can serve as a definite grip on the policy of poverty alleviation.

Nevertheless, the authors look at a number of things that can be used as a reference for current governance to maximize the efforts of poverty testing in the remainder of one year of his reign.

- First, poverty testing through job procurement should strongly consider the level of industrial development and the integration of a country in the world market. Countries such as Indonesia whose industry growth rates are not yet advanced and the informative sector is still very dominating, it is necessary to consider a suitable strategy. The desire to be able to compete in the global market is balanced with various efforts to support small businesses as a base of industrialization.

- Second, developing countries with broad market potential such as Indonesia is very vulnerable to intervention by international financial institutions (World Trade Organization, International Monetary Fund, and World Bank) and developed industrialized countries To open its market and eliminate subsidies. If the request is fulfilled, then no longer will it affect the wage rate of workers that further potential leads to the increasing number of employment disconnection (LAYOFFS). That means the number of poor people in Indonesia will increase more.

- Thirdly, equal opportunity should be given in competition between small and medium enterprises of capital and small business itself. Giving the same opportunity must be implemented through various policies and regulations

- The fourth, mapping the problem and the potential of a country as well as a specific development strategy will only be widely accepted if it is done by involving the entire social and economic layer of society, especially the people who do not have. So, not only involve the entrepreneurs or the people who do. Referring to the above four, in relation to the formulation of poverty testing policy, Indonesia is expected to achieve one of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), which is reducing half the number of poor people. The MDGs is a humanitarian project proclaimed by the United Nations (PBB) for the period of fifteen years (2000-2015). The MDGs are agreed upon by all members of the United Nations, including Indonesia. Thus only seven years the remaining time owned by Indonesia to reduce half the number of poor people.

According to Frances Fox Piven and Richard A Cloward (Regulating the Poor: The Functions of Public Welfare, Vintage Books 1993), poverty includes three aspects (1) material deficiencies and scarcity of basic goods and services, which usually includes the need Daily food, clothing, housing, and health services; (2) Not fulfilling the social needs, including social alienation, dependence, and inability to participate in the community, including in education and information; and (3) lack of adequate income and wealth. The meaning of "adequate " Here is very different, depending on the political and economic context of a country.

Plural poverty occurs in developing countries, but exists in developed countries in the form of homeless communities and ghettos. In Indonesia, according to data on the Poverty Reduction Coordination Team (formed in 2005 through Presidential Decree No. 54, see www.tpkpri.org), the Government has been implementing poverty alleviation programs since the 1960 's through the strategy Fulfillment of the basic needs of the people who are in the national Development Plan eight years (advisors Bede). But the program was stalled halfway through the political crisis of 1965. As for the new order, through Repelita carried out a special strategy to resolve the issue of socio-economic gaps, which conical into the lagging village Inpres program (IDT). However, Orba's efforts failed as a result of the economic and political crisis in 1997.

Those who escape the policy of poverty alleviation in Indonesia

In March 2018 poverty was at a rate of 9.82 percent or 25.95 million poor people. The government then claimed that the number was the lowest poverty rate since the 1998 crisis. To support this claim, BPS released an infographic showing the trend of declining poverty figures in Indonesia in recent years. The low poverty rate is regarded as an achievement in implementing poverty eradication policies since the last two decades.

But if we look at poverty in the wider lens, we need to question the government's claim because there is a group of Indonesians who escape the policy of poverty alleviation. They have continued to have a vulnerability, at one time at the end of the poverty line and the other time below the poverty line. This group, which economists called transient poor groups, struggled all his life not to fall poor, and often failed. But they missed the government's help.

Economists Martin Ravallion of Australia explains that the transient poor population is identified as being below the poverty line, but in the subsequent survey period lies slightly above the poverty line and returns the opportunity The poverty line in the next survey period. Transient poor residents also included people who did not enter the poor category. They are located a little above the poverty line, but have experienced downward movement in the poverty line even though they can crawl up again over the poverty line in the next survey period.

The transient poor people's position is very labil – they are not categorized as poor people and are excluded from poor aid policy schemes but because of their positions which are only slightly above the poverty line, they are very Vulnerable to falling back down the poverty line. Transient poor people are also neglected because the data about them is unavailable.

The survey method conducted by BPS mainly uses cross-sectional technique, which is the technique of collecting data at a certain point in time, unable to detect transient poor population. This technique will not be able to display expense and revenue data by name and address, and cannot see the movement of resident conditions over time.

To see it can only be done with data continuum via longitudinal method, that is, data collection techniques in two or more periods of the survey with the same subject to see the dynamics or progression and do the comparison.

One of the factors that led to an ineffective poverty alleviation policy was the lack of conceptualization of the so-called poor and factors that became the cause. It is clear that poverty alleviation policy in Indonesia does not highlight the cause of the population around the poverty line.

Inclusive and sustainable policies

We are faced with the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a continuation of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). In the SDGs, there are 17 destinations to equally create the earth as a better place. In relation to poverty, the first point is "No Poverty", meaning, at local level, must be sought by poverty alleviation which is of course inclusive and sustainable.

The social environment inclusive means the environment is safe, comfortable and accepting all communities without exception to access social services with the aim of creating a sense of happiness and prosperous conditions. Such conditions will be difficult to achieve when poverty is still a problem and a dilemma. Meanwhile, the size of the poverty line used by BPS clearly must be reconstructed. Dengan apply the wrong method, then the resulting policy will not be maximized.

Given that the cross-sectional method will not be able to comprehensively describe the dynamic and complex conditions of poverty in Indonesia, the most important thing to do is to incorporate a poor transient into the formulation scheme Policy. To achieve this, then the academics, practitioners, observers and of course the government both central and district must understand the concept of poverty in the same frequency.

More than that, the more top down policy of the central government should be changed because it will not be able to actually embrace the public. An inclusive policy is required to formulate poverty alleviation policies in Indonesia.

The recommended poverty alleviation policy is a policy based on community participation by emphasizing the form of empowerment that accommodates the community's local wisdom. We can take the example of the implementation of inclusive development in the city of Solo, especially how the arrangement of Street Vendors

(PKL) was done carefully when it was still the mayor of Solo. Poverty alleviation policies should not be dispersed but pay attention to the distinctive characteristics of each poor community. Thus, the assistance program and the form of empowerment can be more precisely targeted.

World Bank support in reducing poverty in Indonesia

The world Bank continues to cooperate with the Government of Indonesia in an effort to eradicate poverty. Research on poverty and poverty alleviation includes many areas, such as poverty trends, social assistance, social security, community-based programs, and more and better job creation. The research group serves as the basis for providing recommendation of policies and other support from the world Bank to the government of Indonesia. The world Bank also provides technical support for implementing government programs. For example, the PNPM Support Facility provides analytical support and implementation for the national Program of Community Empowerment.

Poverty reduction Program from President Suharto to Jokowi

The Government of Joko Widodo-Jusuf Kalla the period was reduced to 9.82 percent in 2018. This achievement is not only the hard work of the present Government, but also the contributions of the previous government. Special staff of President of Economics, Ahmad Erani Yustika, said every government wants a low level of poverty. This was also addressed through various programs from the Government of President Suharto to President Joko Widodo.

I'm not saying which government is faster. I just wanted to give a message, poverty reduction program so the commitment of all state leaders. Hence, over time, from the time of the new Order of poverty falls, there are numbers.

But what are the government's eradication programs? The following is a summary of poverty alleviation program since President Soeharto until the latest President Joko Widodo

➤ **1970-1998 (Soeharto President)**

1. Inpres Village Left Behind
2. Poor welfare relief Program
3. Self-reliant Young family Program
4. Enhancement of women role programs
5. Construction of Coral cadets and assistance of poor families
6. Increasing the agricultural intensifikasi of food crops
7. Education and health programs
8. Business development of kecil-credit Candak Kulak
9. Transmigration Program
10. Family Welfare Savings (TAKESRA) and Family welfare business credits (KUKESRA)

➤ **1998-1999 (BJ Habibie President)**

1. Social Rescue Network Program (JPS)
2. Rice subsidy for the community
3. Funds for the education of children from poor and prosperous families
4. Scholarships for students are not able to
5. Work-Intensive programs

➤ **2000-2001 (Abdul Rahman Wahid President)**

1. Health and education services for the poor
2. Residential Environment Improvement
3. Development of the poor business culture
4. Subsidies to clean water
5. Compensation for rising FUEL prices in education, health and public transport services

- **2001-2004 (Megawati President)**
 1. Cheap electricity for poor households
 2. Subsidies for underprivileged communities
 3. Interest subsidy for microbusiness credit program
 4. Fertilizer subsidies
 5. Health care
- **2004-2014 (Susilo Bambang Yudoyono President)**
 1. National Community Empowerment Program (PNPM) Independent
 2. Program family Wishes (PKH)
 3. Rice subsidies to poor people (Raskin)
 4. Poor student Assistance (BSM)
 5. Askeskin/Jamkesmas Program
 6. Cash Direct Assistance Program (BLT)
 7. Temporary Community Direct Assistance Program (BLSM)
- **2014-2019 (Jokowi President)**
 1. Indonesia Smart Program (PIP)
 2. Healthy Indonesian Program (PIS)
 3. Program family Harapan (PKH)
 4. Prosperous rice (Rastra) or social food aid
 5. Non-Cash food aid (BPNT)
 6. Village Fund Program
 7. Agrarian reform Program and social forestry (RAPS)

Poverty alleviation

The number of world population 50 last year increased quite drastically especially in developing countries. It is recorded that the world population at 2010 reaches 6.8 billion inhabitants. Even the UN predicts in 2050 the population of the world will increase to 9.2 billion. While in Indonesia based on data from the world Bank, the number of inhabitants recorded has reached $\pm$ 250 million in 2013 and ranks the four countries with the largest population in the world after the PRC, India, and the United States.

The rapid growth of the population is not undeniable is one of the factors that can cause a variety of new problems both economically and socially in society. With the ever increasing number of practical residents cause the primary life needs of the society such as food becomes very high. Meanwhile, natural resources available on Earth both land and commodity materials continue to diminish. In addition, with the number of inhabitants, the need for clean water also becomes very high while the pollution of the river is increasingly worrying that then caused the occurrence of clean water crisis especially in large cities populous population. The height of the population and supported by the high urbanization also inflict negative effects such as slums and poor sanitation levels in the urban consequences, emerging economic and social issues such as health, education, poverty, And unemployment haunting poor families in different parts of the world.

Population growth is not separated from economic issues such as poverty and the increasing number of unemployment. The higher the population, the job field is also reduced so many people find it difficult to get jobs. Lack of employment will eventually lead to an increase in the number of poor people. In addition, the magnitude of the population also leads to the cost required by the Government to provide a variety of basic services such as education and healthcare become increasingly greater. While government finances are very limited especially in poor countries and developing countries. Consequently, it is difficult for the Government to undertake sustainable development to alleviate poverty.

The problem of poverty is the issue for all nations and countries both developed, developing especially poor countries such as many countries in Africa, South America, Western and South Asia. Some of the indicators used by the international world to measure poverty include Headcount Index, Foster-Greer-Thorbecke Index, and Mutidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). But the most commonly used is the Headcount Index, which is

calculating the income per head of the population with an income size of 1.25 dollars per day. The 1.25 dollar size is a set value based on Purchasing Power Parity in the US dollar.

The emergence of various poverty problems due to the high population growth is causing governments in various parts of the world to create a policy to control the rate of population growth especially as it is done in Developed countries, where they are currently experiencing a low birth phase. But unfortunately, in developing countries that happen is the opposite. Population growth in the developing world is very high as is the case in Bangladesh, India, Brazil, and Indonesia. Actually, the population control program in these countries has been conducted. In Indonesia, for example, the control program has been conducted since decades ago through a family planning program (KB). However, the success rate of the program is not very perceived because the fact that Indonesia's population growth is still high. It is also a challenge for us to overcome the growing problem of population growth as well as overcoming poverty issues both in urban and rural areas.

In addition to the control of population growth, several direct policies in poverty alleviation efforts have also been conducted by the Government such as cross subsidy policy, Community Direct Relief Scheme (BLM), granting business capital to Community empowerment, health and education assistance, and other safety net programs. However, efforts to improve the living standards of the poor are not easy, it takes time and consistency and extraordinary efforts by creating a variety of breakthrough and appropriate policies and effective. Further, the policy is made to be able to be implemented in the field according to policy direction with good supervision and evaluation so that does not happen misleading.

One of the interesting policy options in poverty alleviation in Indonesia and still escape from government's attention is the progressive tax for high income communities. The tax imposition for a wealthy community of high income is not a popular policy. However, this progressive tax if applied can help government finances in subsidizing the needs of the poor. Income from progressive taxes can be allocated completely to subsidize the poor through various poverty alleviation programs and other safety nets so that the subsidy budget used during this time can be transferred to Development of a more productive economic sector.

In addition, some policies for poverty alleviation are also interesting to be studied and conducted are human capital development, social capital increase, increase capability through micro business financing (Financial, agricultural, and other businesses). These policies can be done through government cooperation at both local and international levels such as the world Bank and UNDP making it easier and more effective.

Poverty alleviation is ultimately difficult to achieve if the main problem is not well identified. While these direct policies are performed, if the main issue is not included in the policy model it is likely that the policy will not run effectively and will not give a significant change. The real socio-economic problem is the result of very high population growth in recent decades is a major issue in poverty alleviation. Therefore, in addition to efforts to fulfill basic services and safety nets programs and other policies, the efforts to control population growth need to be a more serious concern for the government in carrying out Poverty.

Great cost of poverty alleviation

Many times we hear governments embeds the phrase "first in history" when announcing the level of poverty. Actually, that is the political gimmick that is not important in public policy, because in fact, every decline then the new number has always been the lowest throughout history. Repetition only promises inefficiencies, one important thing to question the poverty alleviation program. Every year the number of poor people go down. However, the budget of poverty alleviation is rising every year. The Government is establishing poverty management in the social protection budget. The objectives, such as in the state Budget income and expenditure (APBN) are for poverty alleviation and empowerment and improvement of community welfare. Various programs are held, such as the family wishes Program, the poor people's rice, and other programs. Every year from 2015 to 2019, social protection costs rose by an average of 10.3 percent, while the number of poor people continued to fall. Ironic, indeed. Because of the decline in poverty that is always being boosted by the government who want to say that the program and utilization of the budget succeeded. Indeed, the government's announcement is still a coma. At the same time, the poor are increasingly poor. This is called the depth of poverty according to the Central statistical body (BPS). As of March 2019, the BPS noted that the poverty depth

index reached 1.55 or an average of 1.67 for a time span of 2015-2019. This figure is larger than the previous five years (2010-2014), which is 1.40. This depth indicator explains one thing.

The average expenditure of poor people in Indonesia is further below the poverty line. Thus, his poverty deepening, so to get out of the group of poor people is harder. The demonic circle of poverty the community experiencing poverty level demonstrates the hellessness of the changes in the cost of goods and services. His income was not able to adapt. Thus, they could potentially be trapped in a vicious circle of poverty or the viscicle of Poverty (Myrdal, 1968). Of course the depth of poverty is hardly ever announced by the government, because it is not politically comfortable. Because this is not an achievement, but a disaster for poverty statistics and groups of poor people. Related to the growing budget while the number of poor people is also very ironic. Questionable efficiency of utilization. For the period of 2015-2018, the average poverty reduction cost has a monthly ratio of 1:23,42 million. This means that the cost to lower poverty per month amounted to Rp 23.42 million per person. Take the example on 2018. At the same year, the Government allocated social protection expenditure in the State budget (APBN) of Rp 173.77 trillion. With that amount of money, it was only able to issue 805 thousand people from the category of poor groups. Thus, in a simple count, the ratio is 1:17,99 million. The most expensive ratio occurred in 2016, i.e. 1:49,02 million.

Of course the cost of tambun tends to be excessive. For example, if there is no poverty alleviation program, then the budget is distributed to all the poor people, it is still surplus to make the whole exit from the poverty line. Causes of inefficient poverty alleviation budget it is a mysterious allocation of poverty budgets increasing amid the number of poor people who continue to fall. There is probably no error in the program that is running, so the cost seems inefficient. Another possibility that is still open is the presence of a non-cash food mafia brace for the poor-as it was established by General Company Bulog (Perum Bulog) lately. Or, it may also be due to the slowing of bureaucratic costs such as meeting expenses, service travel, and various studies. One thing that must have never been heard there is an open evaluation related to the efficiency of poverty reduction.

Moreover, the institution that handles the affairs of poverty alleviation is so much. Among them is the Ministry of Social Affairs, national team of accelerating poverty reduction, and there are also hidden in the Ministry of Health and Ministry of Education. The rise of poverty alleviation committees has made efficiency of budget use difficult to evaluate. Even if there's a mistake or a budget wastage, the odds are on the go. Not excessive if President Joko Widodo consolidated the handling of poverty in one roof. Evaluation of achievements as well as the utilization of budgets became easier and measurable. For example, submitting all the budgets of poverty alleviation in a bag of social ministry, as well as changing its nomenclature to the Ministry of Poverty alleviation and disaster management. Such policies can also be claimed by governments with the "first in history" jargon of consolidating poverty alleviation. Let it remain a gimmick of the poor people well managed because it is empowered, not the other.

5. CONCLUSION

Poverty management requires a concept of integrative cooperation, meaning in overcoming poverty is not enough one field that handles the social service, the existence of the limitations of a service will be enhanced by other areas such as education, health, population, labor, and others, poverty is not just the problem they do not have a job, but there is a tendency for people to choose the job that they want to work In accordance with the discipline of the their knowledge.

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